
The Legal Implications of the Enforcement of International Arbitral Award with Respect to India

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ABSTRACT

This research paper will trace the legal issues relevant to the enforcement of international arbitration awards in India-an essential area for upgrading the country's attractiveness as a destination for foreign investment and international trade. In theory, India has made important formal commitments to international arbitration through accession to the New York Convention as well as the Arbitration and Conciliation Act 1996, yet there remain some critical problems in the enforcement mechanism. Indian courts too frequently interfere with arbitration matters and rely more on the "public policy" exception to deny enforcement, causing unpredictability and delays that would not attract foreign investors. The paper analyses key judicial decisions, legislative amendments and their impacts on enforcement practices, urging the need for a more arbitration-friendly environment. It makes a comparative study of more reputable arbitration jurisdictions, like Singapore and Hong Kong, to find best practices that India could borrow to enhance its legal regime. The bottom line is to provide valuable insights and recommendations to bridge gaps in India's enforcement mechanisms so the arbitration landscape in the country would be relied upon as much more reliable and efficient than international standards.

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INTRODUCTION

The neutrality, adaptability, and enforceability of awards made through international arbitration make it a desirable means of settling cross-border business disputes. Because globalization has stretched up their long arms in reaching multinationals, arbitration caters as a procedure where parties from various countries may resolve their issues out of national courts. Alternative dispute resolution mechanism is more critical to foreign investors and international businesses since they need a credible and effective process among countries where they conduct operations.

India is an emerging economy and a major trading nation that has positioned itself as a jurisdiction for international arbitration. India is a signatory to the New York Convention 1958 on the Recognition and Enforcement of Foreign Arbitral Awards that placed its recognition and enforcement processes under a mandatory legal standard. The Act of Arbitration and Conciliation, 1996, enshrines the UNCITRAL Model Law principles and thus becomes an important body of law upon which arbitration proceedings in India are based, including international awards enforcement provisions.

Despite such formal commitments, enforcement of international arbitration awards in India has been severely questioned. Indian courts have intervened very frequently into arbitration matters and have been consistently denying enforcement under the "public policy" exception. The judicial intervention coupled with tardiness of judicial processes has raised a great concern for the foreign investor and businesses about the certainty and efficiency of arbitration enforcement in India.

Although the Arbitration and Conciliation (Amendment) Acts of 2015 and 2019 have brought about certain much-needed changes to arbitration practices that would effectively reduce judicial intervention and make India an arbitration-friendly jurisdiction, numerous questions still prevail with respect to such change implementation and its practical effectiveness in bringing India's arbitration regime into alignment with international standards.

ENFORCEMENT PROCEDURE UNDER THE NEW YORK CONVENTION

India has signed the New York Convention on the Recognition and Enforcement of Foreign Arbitral Awards, which serves as a fundamental mechanism for the global enforcement of foreign arbitration awards. The New York Convention mandates that member states such as India must acknowledge and implement arbitral awards from other signatory nations when specific criteria are fulfilled.¹

Requirements for Enforcement:

Under the Arbitration and Conciliation Act, a foreign arbitral award can be enforced in India if:

- A. The award is made in a country that is a signatory to the New York Convention.
- B. The award is made in a territory that has been notified by the Indian government as a reciprocating country.

Grounds for Refusal of Enforcement:

Indian courts may refuse to enforce a foreign arbitral award under Section 48 of the Act based on the following grounds:

“Conditions for enforcement of foreign awards.

(1) Enforcement of a foreign award may be refused, at the request of the party against whom it is invoked, only if that party furnishes to the court proof that—

(a) the parties to the agreement referred to in section 44 were, under the law applicable to them, under some incapacity, or the said agreement is not valid under the law to which the parties have subjected it or, failing any indication thereon, under the law of the country where the award was made; or

(b) the party against whom the award is invoked was not given proper notice of the appointment of the arbitrator or of the arbitral proceedings or was otherwise unable to present his case; or

(c) the award deals with a difference not contemplated by or not falling within the terms of the submission to arbitration, or it contains decisions on matters beyond the scope of the submission to arbitration:

Provided that, if the decisions on matters submitted to arbitration can be separated from those not so submitted, that part of the award which contains decisions on matters submitted to arbitration may be enforced; or

(d) the composition of the arbitral authority or the arbitral procedure was not in accordance with the agreement of the parties, or, failing such agreement, was not in accordance with the law of the country where the arbitration took place ; or

(e) the award has not yet become binding on the parties, or has been set aside or suspended by a competent authority of the country in which, or under the law of which, that award was made.

(2) Enforcement of an arbitral award may also be refused if the Court finds that—

- (a) the subject-matter of the difference is not capable of settlement by arbitration under the law of India; or
- (b) the enforcement of the award would be contrary to the public policy of India.”²

- Inadequate party capacity: The entities involved in the arbitration agreement possessed insufficient capacity.
- Arbitration agreement is invalid: The legal system governing the chosen seat declares the arbitration agreement as invalid.
- The enforcement process violated due process standards because the party did not receive notice and a fair hearing opportunity or was unable to present their case.
- Obvious excess of jurisdiction: The award arises from a dispute that has not been referred to arbitration or deals with a matter beyond the scope of the submission to arbitration
- Breach of public policy: The award is contrary to public policy
- Public policy: The award stands in violation of Indian public policy standards. Among the various reasons for refusal, this ground stands as the most contested and frequently subjected to legal proceedings.

PUBLIC POLICY EXCEPTION AND ITS INTERPRETATION

“Section 48: Conditions for enforcement of foreign awards.—

(2) Enforcement of an arbitral award may also be refused if the Court finds that—

(b) the enforcement of the award would be contrary to the public policy of India.”³

Indian courts have made many loud statements regarding foreign arbitral award enforcement public policy exceptions which directly led to the clarification in Section 48(2)(b) Arbitration and Conciliation Act that judges can deny awards contradicting India's public policy. The broad judicial interpretation of public policy by Indian courts continues to make intervention in arbitral awards perhaps the most effective method of objection.

Judicial Interpretation

Indian courts have evolved the interpretation of public policy through various landmark judgments:

Renusagar Power Co. Ltd. v. General Electric Co. (1994): The Supreme Court in this ruling established that violations of fundamental policies of Indian law coupled with Indian interests and justice or morality could invoke the public policy exception. The court established an award refusal guideline through public policy exceptions that operate under certain precise conditions.⁴

ONGC v. Saw Pipes Ltd. (2003): SC extended the public policy exception towards arbitral awards to also include "patent illegality." That enlarged scope provided more scope for the courts to examine, then results in more challenges for enforcement.⁵

Shri Lal Mahal Ltd. v. Progetto Grano Spa (2013): The Supreme Court clarified here that the wider public policy test as laid down in *Saw Pipes* would come into play only about domestic awards, whereas a narrower one, as set out in *Renusagar*, would apply to foreign awards. It could of course be appreciated that this is something of an abrogation of its earlier decisions and represents a welcome return to a more arbitration-friendly approach when it comes to the enforcement of international awards.⁶

Bhatia International v. Bulk Trading S.A. (2002): In this case, the Supreme Court ruled that the provisions of Part I of the Arbitration Act, which deal with domestic arbitration, would apply even to international commercial arbitrations unless expressly excluded by the parties. This led to greater judicial intervention in international arbitrations seated outside India, a decision that was later overruled.⁷

BALCO (Bharat Aluminium Co. v. Kaiser Aluminium Technical Services Inc., 2012): The landmark ruling of *BALCO* reversed *Bhatia International*, and it was held that Part I of the Arbitration Act would not apply to arbitrations seated outside India. This has caused a considerable shrinkage of judicial intervention in foreign-seated arbitrations.⁸

Venture Global Engineering v. Satyam Computer Services Ltd. (2008): This case presented complications arising out of public policy challenges, wherein the Supreme Court refused the enforcement of a foreign arbitral award due to potential violation of Indian public policy.⁹

Recent Amendments and Judicial Trends:

In the effort to further curtail judicial intervention, the Arbitration and Conciliation (Amendment) Act, 2015¹⁰ simplified the scope of public policy challenges in international arbitration, such that it only

applied to issues related to a violation of the fundamental policy of Indian law, basic notions of morality or justice, fraud in the arbitral process, and corruption in the conducting of those arbitral proceedings. The 2019 Amendment further worked on how this rule of minimal judicial intervention could further the principle of finality in arbitration.¹¹ The Indian legal architecture relating to enforcement of international arbitration awards is robust, but it has been challenged by extremely serious issues regarding judicial overreach and expansive interpretation of the "public policy exception." Legislative reforms have entered the fray in order to correct such issues, but much more will be required to ensure that the Indian arbitration regime catches up with the best international practices and improves its reputation as a reliable venue for international arbitration.¹²

COMPARISON BETWEEN INDIA VS. SINGAPORE, HONGKONG AND UK

Such an analysis of this framework of arbitration in India and other important jurisdictions that offer arbitration friendly mechanism for enforcement of internationally awarded would be critical for the positioning of the positives and the less positives of this mechanism of India. It has been established as hubs for arbitration globally in Singapore, Hong Kong and the UK with an efficient, predictable and consistent enforcement regime. For the knowledge of how such jurisdictions handle arbitration, one will know how India should bring its arbitration regime to its best practice such that having pursued best practices in that sphere, may work to best practices in its appointment sphere, amongst others.

Singapore

Singapore has become one of the preferred venues for international arbitration because of its relatively benevolent pro-arbitration legal framework that features low judicial intervention. Out of the world's top arbitration institutions, the SIAC is located in Singapore. The Singapore arbitration law is formed under the UNCITRAL Model Law.

Legal Framework:

The International Arbitration Act, 1994, governs international arbitration in Singapore and includes the New York Convention.¹³ The pro-arbitration attitude of the Singapore courts permits court interference only if the same is absolutely warranted. The scope of setting aside or refusing enforcement of foreign awards, on public policy grounds, is so narrow that there might not be much scope for such actions. The Singapore courts strictly apply the principle that an arbitral award has a final quality; in other words, it does not tolerate interference. Unless a circumstance arises showing public policy being affected, or

established cases of fraud and procedural impropriety appear, it is very unlikely that the Singaporean courts would intervene in the arbitration process or decree enforcement against an arbitration award. The ambit for a public policy exception is restricted in Singapore.

Hong Kong

Other arbitration-friendly laws, infrastructures, as well as a strategic location that is a gateway to China have made Hong Kong another leader in arbitration. Like Singapore, the legal system for the arbitration in Hong Kong is also based on the UNCITRAL Model Law and the New York Convention.

Thus, Hong Kong offers a well-connected city with good infrastructure, hotels and arbitration facilities, a modern legal system for arbitration that is being refreshed, and in the HKIAC, an institution that has grown over the last years to rival longer-established bodies. With the arrival of the ICC Secretariat international parties now also have a choice of institution.¹⁴

Legal Framework:

International arbitration is governed by the Arbitration Ordinance (Cap. 609) in Hong Kong. That implies a thorough UNCITRAL Model Law and vast provisions on how to enforce foreign arbitral awards. Generally, the pro-enforcement policy applied by the Hong Kong judiciary tends to allow for virtually few grounds to set aside or refuse the enforcement of an award. One of the most important guiding principles is judicial non-intervention, which enhances the autonomy of arbitration. In Hong Kong, like in Singapore, the public policy exception is narrowly construed. Repeatedly, courts have held public policy objections an inappropriate tool to look at the merits of an award. The Hong Kong International Arbitration Centre (HKIAC) ranks among the world's leading arbitration institutions. Indeed, rules and procedures are designed to be fair and efficient within the arbitration process.

United Kingdom (UK)

The UK, and London in particular, is the global center in international arbitration. One discovers predictable legal framework, minimal court interference, and the long history of supporting arbitration as a shrewd method of dispute resolution with the UK..

Legal Framework:

The first is that the arbitration is according to the provisions of the Arbitration Act 1996 of England and Wales and of Northern Ireland. This, unlike India's Arbitration and Conciliation Act, 1996 has greater party autonomy and arbitral awards finality. Judges of the UK even as highly amenable to arbitration and does not intervene in the courts. The grounds on which awards can be set aside are very limited and comprise by way of example only, lack of jurisdiction, serious procedural irregularity and breach of public policy. The application of the public policy defense has been abhorred in the British courts from time immemorial and it is settled that the defense ought to be applied only in circumstances where the enforcement would be against a most rudimentary principle of justice or morality. One of the strengths of UK's arbitration framework is that it gives finality to the arbitral award. Respecting the arbitral award and far less likely of any applications for challenges of awards, the English courts accord full respect to arbitral awards rendered in the UK and foreign.

COMPARATIVE INSIGHTS

Under this aspect, both Singapore and Hong Kong developed a philosophy of non-interventionism on the part of the judiciary. Indian courts have generally intervened in arbitration matters much more frequently throughout their history. Limiting court intervention in India strictly to situations of procedural injustice or outright violation of public policy would enhance the country's reliability on arbitration. A narrow interpretation of the public policy exception in Singapore, Hong Kong, and the UK ensures enforcement of foreign arbitral awards only rarely is denied. Indian courts have been more expansive in interpreting the public policy, and their expansive scope for looking into other matters brings uncertainty to enforcement. India has improved manyfold in streamlining the timelines in arbitration but still lags on the parameter of swiftness in enforcing awards. Enforcement in India may be expedited if procedural reforms are opted for, and a separate arbitration bench is constituted. World-class arbitration institutions developed in Singapore and Hong Kong have also significantly contributed to increased global stature of the two jurisdictions. India has promising infrastructure and expertise that can be availed to promote MCIA. Further development is, however required before India can become an arbitration-friendly venue for international arbitration.

Comparative analysis reveals that, on many counts, India has done well with the reforms in the arbitration regime; however, there are also areas where India can learn from the arbitration-friendly jurisdictions. Following a tighter definition of public policy, lowering judicial intervention, and making this process more efficient would make India a much more reliable country for holding international

arbitration. The strengthening of arbitration institutions and the making of robust support structures for arbitration proceedings will go only to make it comparable with some of the world's top arbitration centers, like Singapore, Hong Kong, and the United Kingdom (UK).

“Arbitration's effectiveness will always depend upon how well it satisfies the needs of the parties. A draftsman contemplating the insertion of an arbitration clause in an agreement between a developing country and a foreign investor should first acquire a basic understanding of the attitudes of the developing country toward arbitration. If he is dealing with one of the countries of the Middle East, he ought to know that they have long recognized arbitration as a form of dispute settlement. However, despite this recognition, many of these same countries hesitate to enforce awards of foreign arbitral tribunals or to accept the application of foreign law to the resolution of conflicts involving a state entity. Under such circumstances, such countries prefer to resort to their National Courts.”¹⁵

JUDICIAL INTERVENTION AND INTERPRETATION OF PUBLIC POLICY

“Expansion of the public policy exception is perhaps one of the gravest challenges for India when it comes to the enforcement of international arbitration awards.”¹⁶ “Section 48 of the Arbitration and Conciliation Act permits Indian courts not to enforce foreign awards if they appear to be contrary to the public policy of India.”¹⁷ Although the 2015 amendments were made to limit the exclusion to cases of fraud, corruption, or gross violations of public policy, courts still retain much discretion over what constitutes public policy.

Thus, Indian courts have traditionally understood public policy quite broadly; economic or national interest often come as issues within public policy. This threatens the peril that foreign arbitral awards be militated on grounds which do not have any affinity with the basic principles of justice, morality, or law. For example, in cases such as “*ONGC v. Saw Pipes Ltd. (2003)*”¹⁸, by making "patent illegality" a constituent of the definition, this brings an award under judicial scrutiny in a manner arguably more stringent than what is permitted in international practice.

Indian Courts were neither particular in their application of public policy. The “*Renusagar Power Co. Ltd. v. General Electric Co.*”¹⁹ case in (1994) set a very high threshold where a foreign arbitral award could be declined enforcement on public policy grounds. Since then, subsequent judgements in the cases such as “*Venture Global Engineering v. Satyam Computer Services Ltd.*”²⁰ have caused enough

confusion. This uncertainty creates unpredictability for foreign investors and business enterprises desirous of enforcing awards in India.

The diverse and disparate application of public policy challenges raises a climate where foreign arbitral awards are more likely to be challenged. This, therefore, adds time, expense, and uncertainty to the enforcement process.

DELAYS AND PROCEDURAL INEFFICIENCIES

The other major hurdle in the enforcement of international arbitration awards in India is the time lag associated with judicial proceedings. Indian courts are known to have heavy volumes but also take time, and it takes considerable amounts of time to clear through foreign awards under execution. Indian courts suffer from a huge backlog at trial and appellate levels which further aggravates the time lag associated with the resolution of disputes and, therefore, with arbitration enforcement matters as well²¹.

Although the 2015 and 2019 amendments have filled in some time limitations on arbitration proceedings, that limitation is not necessarily available at the enforcement stage, where delay continues. When one party wants to avert or delay enforcement, he could file an interlocutory appeal or apply for a stay order. Indian courts, even after the reforms, tend to hand out interim relief, so that the enforceability of an arbitral award is prolonged through litigation, which may severely dilute the speed and efficiency expected from arbitration. The enforcement of a foreign arbitral award is also not without a series of procedural steps including the filing of petitions, furnishing certified copies of the arbitral award and other documentation requirements which at times creates an additional delay. In some cases, it leads to technical grounds for additional litigation, thus creating another obstacle for its execution. Procedural inefficiencies and judicial delays run counter to the arbitral benefits because parties seeking speed in the resolution of their disputes may be bogged down in interminable litigation.

JUDICIAL ATTITUDES AND RELUCTANCE TO CEDE CONTROL

While the legal reforms move to check judicial overreach, the Indian judiciary is typically very conservative in its outlook, and many judges would not want to lose control over dispute resolution to an arbitration tribunal when it involves high stakes of money or national interest.

“Indian courts, especially the lower courts, seem to lean towards litigations and treat arbitration as less authoritative in settling disputes. Such a conservative view leads to easy challenge of arbitration awards

on grounds of 'jurisdictional defects,' procedural irregularities, or violation of public policy.”²² Even when the award is ordered by a lower court to be enforced, the process may still run into a roadblock from the appellate review. At this stage, the High Courts closely review the award and the order of enforcement and thereby involve a wide-ranging review and possibility of an appeal, which makes the enforcement of arbitral awards complex and time consuming.

Conservative judicial mindset and the likelihood of an over-scrutiny by appellate courts discourage parties from going for arbitration since they fear that the advantages of arbitration, speed and finality, would be dissipated by expensive judicial process.

LACK OF SPECIALIZED ARBITRATION COURTS

Dedicated arbitration benches have been established but specialization in arbitral jurisprudence is still sorely missed in India. Often, subject matters of arbitration may involve knowledge of international legal frameworks, complex commercial agreements or sector-specific regulations that cannot be dealt with by generalist courts even-handedly. Places like Singapore and the UK have very successfully created specialized arbitration courts in which judges are properly trained and have expertise in arbitration law. In India, with few exceptions of some high courts creating arbitration benches, the enforcement matters are largely a subject of generalist judges who do not carry such knowledge; this leads to both inconsistent rulings and an unnecessary delay. Often, the judges in India do not just so happen to be trained in international arbitration law and hence, misaligned with global arbitration practices, are often the decisions that they pass. This results in the application of the law amiss in the case of complex arbitration agreements or foreign awards. “In the absence of specialized arbitration courts, enforcement proceedings are not effective and take time. And the wrong judges hearing the cases of arbitration on sensitive issues sometimes result in unpredictable or inconsistent judgments in the enforcement of foreign awards.”²³

CONCLUSION

This research, therefore, focuses on the legal implications that are critical for the enforcement of international arbitration awards within India—an area where much work has been done, yet a lot is still left behind. India has already built up a sound legal framework under the Arbitration and Conciliation Act of 1996 and its subsequent amendments; yet high judicial interference and expansive interpretations

of the exception based on "public policy" continue to undermine the predictability and reliability that are vital to attracting foreign investment. A comparative analysis with some arbitration-friendly jurisdictions, like Singapore and Hong Kong, and other developed nations, such as the UK, shows that India can harvest the fruits of a more restrictive public policy interpretation, reduction in court intrusion, and procedural efficiencies.

Clearly, these findings reveal that for India to emerge as a venue of choice for international arbitration, it needs not only to bring in its practices in line with international standards but also has to work upon improving the culture for judicial restraint. Dedicated arbitration benches and domestic arbitration institutions such as the MCIAC will further help India as an arbitration destination.

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